

The ASEAN Primary Care Research Excellence Framework (APREF)- The Preliminary Report

The full report is being drafted by

Boon How Chew¹; chewboonhow@upm.edu.my; chewboonhow@gmail.com

Dr. Apichai Wattanapisit²; apichai.wa@gmail.com

Galih Kunarso³; galih.kunarso@singhealth.com.sg

Shih Ying Gun⁴; gun.shih.ying@singhealth.com.sg

Indah Suci Widyahening⁵; indah_widyahening@ui.ac.id

Chirk Jenn Ng⁶; ng.chirk.jenn@singhealth.com.sg

Ngiap Chuan Tan⁷; Tan.Ngiap.Chuan@singhealth.com.sg

Affiliation

¹Professor and Consultant Family Medicine Specialist at Hospital Sultan Abdul Aziz Shah (HSAAS) Teaching Hospital, Universiti Putra Malaysia.

²Associate Professor of Family Medicine at the School of Medicine, Walailak University, Thailand.

³Associate Consultant with SingHealth Polyclinics - Tampines, Singapore.

⁴Accredited Family Physician with SingHealth Polyclinics.

⁵Professor of Community Medicine at the Faculty of Medicine, Universitas Indonesia and Head of Primary Health Care Research and Innovation Center of the Indonesia Medical Education and Research Institute.

⁶Clinical Professor at Duke-NUS Medical School, Singapore; Senior Consultant and Deputy Director of Research at SingHealth Polyclinics.

⁷Clinical Associate Professor, Vice-chairperson, Research Domain, Family Medicine Academic Clinical Program in Duke NUS Medical School, Singapore; Director in Research Department in SingHealth Polyclinics (SHP).

Research Excellence Domains

The APREF's conceptual framework revolves around the quadruple aims: care, health, cost, and healthcare team well-being. Research within APREF is evaluated based on these domains, focusing on health outcomes (physical, metabolic, cognitive, mental, psychosocial), healthcare systems (services, programs, delivery, policy), costs (financing, co-payment), and the research team's well-being. Additionally, APREF emphasizes the need for a clear translation plan to ensure research findings are applied to clinical practice, healthcare services, access, cost, policy, and improving the well-being of healthcare professionals in local settings.

Methods

The development of the ASEAN Primary Care Research Excellence Framework (APREF) took place over two intensive days from 16–17 February 2024 in Singapore, with the goal of establishing a comprehensive framework for assessing primary care research excellence across ASEAN. The activities during this period were structured to incorporate best practices from global research assessment methods. The final output was a rubric presented in the Results section.

The first day began with presentations on global challenges in research assessment, drawing examples from frameworks like the UK's Research Excellence Framework (REF) and similar models in other countries. These presentations provided an overview of how existing research assessment frameworks were designed and implemented, highlighting key concerns such as the over-reliance on publication metrics and grant funding. Following this, each ASEAN country representative gave a presentation on the current state of research assessment in their respective countries, including Indonesia, Malaysia, Singapore, and Thailand. This provided an understanding of the diverse approaches and

limitations within the region, such as varying levels of resources, researcher capacity, and institutional priorities. During the subsequent discussion, the participants identified common issues in research assessment across ASEAN, including the need for contextual relevance, inclusivity of innovation metrics, and avoiding an overemphasis on numerical outputs.

The second day was dedicated to iterative development of the APREF framework. Participants broke down the complex issue of research excellence into more manageable parts. They discussed and ranked the importance of different components such as research quality, impact on healthcare and societal relevance to ensure that the framework covered both quantitative and qualitative aspects of research evaluation. Every research stage at which it could be assessed, from the planning phase (context and input) through to the final outcomes and impacts was considered. The focus was on ensuring that the framework captured not just the outputs of research (e.g., publications, patents) but also the processes and support structures (e.g., mentorship, collaboration) that lead to sustainable research development. Through these methods, the team worked on identifying key metrics and their weightings within the rubric to prioritize criteria based on their relevance to primary care research excellence. This helped us to understand how different components of research could be evaluated proportionately, without placing undue emphasis on a single metric, such as publication count.

Finally, we visually mapped out the relationships between the inputs (resources, researcher experience), activities (research processes), outputs (publications, policies), and outcomes (impact on healthcare, community benefits) of primary care research. This approach was integrated to ensure that the assessment metrics balanced research excellence across multiple dimensions, such as academic rigor, societal impact, and innovation. The result of these activities was a comprehensive rubric designed to assess primary care research excellence in the ASEAN region. The rubric accounted for both quantitative measures (e.g., publications, grants) and qualitative contributions (e.g., societal impact, innovation, healthcare system improvements). Each metric was weighted according to its relevance to the overarching goals of primary care improvement and regional health outcomes, ensuring a balanced and contextually relevant assessment framework. APREF is perceived to be clear, standardized rubrics with well-defined criteria and performance levels. It is to be tested of its relevancy, consistency and transparency in how research from different ASEAN countries would be evaluated, while accounting for regional diversity.

Results

In assessing the performance of research, APREF considers various factors: available data, data sources (e.g., open access or institutional reports), and the specific indices across research domains. The approach to computation and the expertise of assessors (internal or external) are crucial for the accuracy and relevance of evaluation. The framework also examines the resources required for evaluations, the frequency of evaluations, and the report format whether formative or summative. Stakeholders and target recipients, including primary care research centres, are crucial in utilizing the evaluation reports for accreditation and further development of research excellence.

Metrics and Impact Measurement

The APREF uses both traditional and modern metrics to measure research excellence. Traditional metrics include publication counts, citation indices, journal impact factors, grant income, and the number of graduate student degrees awarded. Meanwhile, web-based metrics, such as Altmetrics, focus on the social media influence of research. The framework also tracks the number and type of communications with businesses, government agencies, and NGOs that result in policy changes. Case studies and narratives are used to demonstrate the real-world impact of research. The Stanford Business Impact Compass is a tool used to gauge research impact.

Deliverables and Research Outputs

APREF evaluates research outputs by considering the number of publications in top-tier journals, as well as findings that influence clinical practice guidelines and healthcare policies. The framework also measures interventions that result in cost-effective outcomes, as well as media reports and public health education materials that advance public interest. Furthermore, APREF tracks collaborative projects with other research institutes and technology transfers to industry, including licensing revenue and spin-off support. APREF emphasizes the importance of collaborative research networks, particularly in promoting interdisciplinary and cross-sector research. Collaboration between universities, research institutions, government agencies, and healthcare organizations allows for a more integrated approach to tackling primary care issues. Mentorship programs are crucial for nurturing early-career researchers, providing them with guidance from experienced researchers. These initiatives ensure continuity in research excellence and foster a culture of peer support and knowledge exchange within the region.

Quantitative and qualitative metrics are essential for assessing the effectiveness of the research ecosystem offering insights into the impact of researchers, outputs, administrators, and institutional policies. Research outputs that impact the professional practice, local community, nation and the world could and should in return affect the existing institution's research policies and research office's supports that would impact the researchers within the institution (Figure 1). This could either cause them to be enhanced or dispirited from scientific research, and the level of research standards and continue to relevant to the world.

Figure 1: Important research ecosystem's actors and their contribution and impact assessment

The quantitative and qualitative metrics of the different research actors

Quantitative and qualitative metrics play a crucial role in evaluating the effectiveness and impact of various actors within the research ecosystem including researchers, research outputs, and administrators (Table 2). These metrics provide insight into the quality and scope of research, the broader impacts of research outputs, and the responsiveness of institutional research policies and supports.

Table 2: Quantitative and Qualitative Metrics for Various Research Stakeholders

No.	Actors	Roles	Quantitative Metric (Number and derivatives)	Qualitative Metric
1.	Researchers	Researchers are the main actors, and are the sole producers of research outputs	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Number of researchers - Dr/nurses/AHP as principal investigator or co-investigator 2. Number of grant application 3. Number and amount of grants/ funding 4. Recognition 5. MoU/ MoA 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Type of researchers: Dr/ nurses/AHP 2. Types of grants: seed/local/competitive/industry 3. Qualification of researchers: - research related training (MSc/ PhD/ etc) 4. Experience of researcher as a reviewer 5. External recognition of researcher 6. Quality of partners and objectives in MoU/ MoA
2.	Outputs	Direct or indirect products and effects from research projects	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. PhD/masters in research /post-doc 2. Number of posters/ oral /plenary presentations, etc 3. Publication (book/ papers) 4. IP products eg. Patent, trademark, copyright, invention disclosure etc. 5. Patient education material 6. Revenue generated 7. Number adopted by external institutions 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Graduates succeed in market places 2. Reputable publishers 3. Highly regarded conferences 4. Research products eg. Patient education materials are translated and used in other countries 5. Target users of large groups or of high repute
3.	Impacts	Impacts come directly from research outputs, and as feedback to the research policy and research supports.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. citations/ H-index/ Altmetric score/ institution H-index 2. media/ social media coverage 3. number of work cited by CPG(s)/ national policy changes 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. high-level citation eg. international authoritative guidelines, etc 2. Improved health outcomes on target population 3. Influence practice and policy change 4. Improve research methods 5. reduce healthcare cost 6. improve health/ socioeconomic of the local community 7. improve global health

4.	Administrators	Administrators are all levels of staff that support the researchers especially those in the research office	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Number of support staff-admin/ analytics 2. Number of trained mentor 3. Number and duration of successful IP filing 4. Data stewards 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Type of support staff: admin/ analytics and their highest professional qualification 2. Support staff in trained certain skillset 3. Feedback from researchers, collaborators, industry partners, stakeholders and policymakers
5.	Research supports	Research supports are that provided by the administrators at the research office, or that facilitated by them from external resources.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. In-house training 2. Training program for mentors 3. Mentor(s) 4. Formal mentorship program(s) 5. Number of formal peer support activities-academic (JC)/ social 6. Idea generation activities 7. Patient and public involvement 8. Research consultation clinic and biostatistics clinic 9. Unit to facilitate collaborations- to identify suitable collaborators/ research network/ international/ industrial engagement 10. Data stewardship, FAIR principles 11. Database(s) of journals 12. Research tools and software: NVivo/SPSS 13. computer 14. EMR (amenable for research) 15. New technologies 16. Online automatic updating researcher's performance (eg. SINTA) 17. Access to legal support 18. Research dissemination event 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Evidence-based approaches as much as possible 2. Well-structured and thoughtful sessions 3. World-class program content and trainers 4. Recognitions from different groups of people 5. Dynamic and flexible to the challenges faced by researchers and administrators 6. Feedback from researchers, collaborators, industry partners, stakeholders and policymakers

5.	Institution	Institution is the organisation that provide resources to researchers through multiple channels especially through the administrators at a dedicated research office.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Establish clear research policy 2. Have world-class research office 3. Number of training supported by institution 4. Number of recognition 5. MoU/ MoA 6. Institution ranking on national or international platforms 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. International standards of the research policy 2. Researcher-friendly culture 3. World-class trainings for those involved in research 4. External recognition of researcher/ institution 5. Quality of partners and objectives in MoU/ MoA
6.	Research policy	Research policy is that of own institution, higher authorities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Organization chart 2. Vision & mission 3. Research governance: code of ethics 4. Protected research time 5. High-quality research culture 6. Incentives to undertake research 7. Research integrity training and monitoring/investigation 8. Open science research 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Clearly distributed responsibility 2. Inspiring and achievable vision and mission statements 3. Aligned with international standards 4. Regular reviews of policy by all 5. Expand of open science practice 6. Dynamic and flexible to the challenges faced by researchers and administrators 7. Feedback from researchers, collaborators, industry partners, stakeholders and policymakers

AHP = Allied Health Professionals; CPG(s) = Clinical Practice Guideline(s); EMR = Electronic Medical Record; FAIR = Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (data principles); IP = Intellectual Property; JC = Journal Club; MSc = Master's Science degree (research-related); MoA = Memorandum of Agreement; MoU = Memorandum of Understanding; PhD = Doctor of Philosophy; PI = Principal Investigator; SINTA = Science and Technology Index (for online automatic updating of researcher's performance)

Researchers are the primary contributors to research outputs, and their role can be assessed through both quantitative and qualitative metrics. Quantitatively, key indicators include the number of researchers (categorized as doctors, nurses, or allied health professionals), the number of grant applications submitted, the amount and value of grants awarded, and the number of signed MoUs or MoAs. Number and type of recognition, both in terms of internal and external accolades, further demonstrates impact. Qualitative metrics focus on the type and experience of researchers including their qualifications (such as MCI, PhD), their role as reviewers to different types of publications and funders, and their content of the reviews in terms of quality and length, the diversity of grants they secure (seed, local, competitive, industry), and the quality of collaborations and objectives within MoUs or MoAs.

Research outputs represent the tangible and intangible products or effects generated from research projects. Quantitative indicators include the number of PhD, master's, or post-doctoral graduates, presentations delivered (posters, oral, plenary), published works (books, papers), intellectual property (IP) products such as patents, trademarks, copyrights, and invention disclosures, as well as patient education materials, revenue generated, and the number of research outcomes adopted by external institutions. The qualitative assessment of research outputs provides valuable insights into the broader impact and significance of a researcher's work. The success of graduates (PhD, master's, post-doc) in

the marketplace reflects the practical application and relevance of the research training they received. Publications in reputable journals or by well-regarded publishers underscore the quality and credibility of the research. Similarly, presenting at prestigious conferences highlights the researcher's prominence and the recognition of their work within the academic community. The adoption of research products, such as patient education materials, by international institutions or in other countries further demonstrates the global applicability and influence of the research. Additionally, when target users include large or highly reputable organizations, it indicates the trust and value placed on the research outcomes by prominent stakeholders. Together, these qualitative metrics provide a more comprehensive view of the lasting impact of research beyond mere outputs.

The impact of research can be measured using both quantitative and qualitative metrics, offering a comprehensive view of its reach and significance. Quantitatively, research impact is assessed through citation metrics like the H-index, Altmetric score, and institutional H-index, which reflect the research's influence in academic circles. Media and social media coverage highlight its visibility and public engagement, while the number of works cited by clinical practice guidelines (CPGs) or national policy changes demonstrates its direct influence on healthcare practices and governance. Qualitatively, citations in authoritative international guidelines underscore the research's credibility and role in shaping global standards. The scope of influence of these guidelines should also be outlined. Improvements in health outcomes for target populations provide evidence of the research's real-world impact, with descriptions of the specific health outcomes and the extent of policy influence required. Research that drives changes in policy or practice shows its capacity to effect meaningful transformations in healthcare systems or other sectors. In addition, explaining how innovations enhance research methods and contribute to scientific advancement is crucial. Reductions in healthcare costs, when compared to traditional care or historical data, illustrate the research's economic efficiency. Finally, positive effects on the health and socioeconomic conditions of local communities, as well as contributions to global health, emphasize the research's broad societal impact.

Administrators play a vital role in supporting researchers by providing essential administrative and analytical services, with their impact assessed through both quantitative and qualitative metrics. Quantitatively, key indicators include the number of support staff in administrative and analytical roles, the number of trained mentors available to guide researchers, the number and duration of successful intellectual property (IP) filings, and the presence of data stewards who efficiently manage research data. Qualitatively, the type and level of expertise of the support staff, along with their highest qualifications and any additional formal or on-the-job professional training, are critical in determining the quality of assistance provided to researchers. The specialized skill sets of support staff highlight the institution's commitment to building a knowledgeable and capable administrative team. Feedback from researchers, collaborators, industry partners, stakeholders, and policymakers offers valuable insights into the effectiveness and responsiveness of administrative support. Positive feedback suggests that administrators are not only facilitating research operations but also fostering collaboration and ensuring smooth interactions with external partners.

Research support refers to the resources and assistance provided by research office administrators or sourced externally. Quantitative metrics for evaluating research support can be tracked through the number of in-house training sessions conducted annually and participation rates in these programs. The effectiveness of mentor training programs is measured by the number of mentors trained each year, while the availability of mentorship is gauged by the number of active mentors. Formal mentorship programs are assessed by the number of programs implemented and the level of participant engagement. Other trackable metrics include the number of formal academic and social peer support activities, idea generation events, public and patient involvement (PPI) initiatives, and research consultation or biostatistics clinics. Collaborations facilitated by a dedicated unit can be quantified by the number of identified collaborators, research networks, and industrial or international

engagements. Additional metrics include the availability of data stewardship tools following FAIR principles, the number of accessible journal databases, research tools and software (e.g., NVivo, SPSS), computers, EMR systems for research, and newly introduced technologies. Automated tracking of researcher performance via platforms like SINTA, the availability of legal support, and the number of research dissemination events also contribute to quantitative assessments. Qualitative metrics for research support focus on the depth and quality of the provided resources. This includes evaluating how evidence-based the training programs and mentorship initiatives are, and how well-structured and thoughtfully planned the sessions are. The quality of content and delivery is assessed by the extent to which programs are perceived as world-class and led by expert trainers. Recognition from researchers, administrators, and external stakeholders underscores the program's prestige. Flexibility and adaptability in addressing the evolving challenges faced by researchers and administrators are key indicators of a program's responsiveness. Feedback from researchers, collaborators, industry partners, stakeholders, and policymakers offer critical insights into the perceived effectiveness, satisfaction, and impact of the support, helping to refine future initiatives.

Quantitative metrics for evaluating an institution's support for researchers include the establishment of clear research policies and the presence of a world-class research office. The number of training programs offered by the institution, along with the recognition or awards received by its researchers, demonstrates its commitment to fostering research excellence. Additionally, the number of Memorandums of Understanding (MoUs) and Agreements (MoAs) signed with other organizations highlights the institution's level of collaboration and partnerships. The institution's ranking on national and international platforms further serves as a measurable indicator of its standing and reputation in the global research community. Qualitative metrics focus on how well the institution's research policies align with international standards, ensuring they meet global benchmarks for excellence. A researcher-friendly culture is evaluated by the extent to which the institution fosters a supportive, inclusive, and innovative environment. The quality of training programs is assessed by their adherence to world-class standards, ensuring that both researchers and staff are equipped with best practices. External recognition, such as awards or acknowledgments of both researchers and the institution, reflects its reputation and prestige. Lastly, the quality of partnerships and the strategic objectives outlined in MoUs and MoAs signal the institution's commitment to meaningful collaborations and impactful research initiatives.

Quantitative metrics for evaluating a research policy may include the presence of a well-defined organizational chart and a clear articulation of the institution's vision and mission. Key indicators of ethical and sustainable research practices include the implementation of research governance, such as a formal code of ethics, and the allocation of dedicated research time for faculty. The institution's commitment to fostering a high-quality research culture can be assessed through the number of incentives offered to researchers—such as grants and rewards—and the frequency of research integrity training sessions, along with processes for monitoring and investigation. Support for open science initiatives can be measured by the number of open-access publications and participation in open research data-sharing platforms. Qualitative metrics for assessing a research policy involve examining how clearly responsibilities are distributed within the organization, ensuring roles are well-defined and understood by all stakeholders. The institution's vision and mission statements should be both inspiring and achievable, providing a clear purpose to guide research activities. Alignment with international standards ensures the policy adheres to global best practices. Regular reviews by researchers, administrators, and other relevant parties demonstrate a commitment to continuous improvement. The expansion of open science practices further highlights the institution's dedication to transparency and collaboration. Flexibility in addressing evolving challenges faced by researchers and administrators is a key indicator of the policy's adaptability. Finally, feedback from researchers, collaborators, industry partners, stakeholders, and policymakers offers valuable insights into the policy's effectiveness and relevance, helping to shape future directions.

The reverse impacts of research outputs to the research institutions

The impact of research outputs on professional practice, the local community, the nation, and the international community can significantly shape institutional research policies, and the support systems offered to researchers. Whether these effects are positive or negative, they influence researchers' motivation and the overall quality and relevance of their work.

When research positively impacts professional practice, local communities, or national and global systems, institutions may respond by revising their policies to prioritize high impact, applied research. This could lead to increased funding, enhanced collaboration opportunities with professional bodies or external organizations, and a stronger emphasis on research that addresses real-world problems. Researchers are further motivated when their contributions are recognized and rewarded through institutional acknowledgment or career advancement opportunities. For instance, local partnerships with governments or NGOs can foster socially responsible research, and international collaborations can boost global visibility and recognition. Such institutional support enhances researcher engagement, encouraging the pursuit of innovative and high-quality work that can influence practices, policies, and standards at various levels.

Conversely, if research outputs are undervalued or unsupported, negative effects can arise. When researchers feel that their contributions to professional practice, local communities, or national and international advancements are not sufficiently acknowledged, they may become discouraged. A lack of institutional support for translating research into practice, insufficient resources for community-engaged projects, or limited recognition for contributions to national or global issues may result in diminished enthusiasm for pursuing impactful research. If global recognition is prioritized at the expense of local or national relevance, researchers working on region-specific challenges might feel alienated, further eroding their motivation.

In response to these dynamics, institutions must ensure that their research policies and support systems are flexible, adaptive, and inclusive. Policies that prioritize innovation, collaboration, and the real-world application of research will help sustain a motivated and engaged research community. At the same time, robust recognition and reward systems are essential to valuing the diverse impacts of research—whether at the local, national, or international level—fostering a culture of excellence and relevance across all areas of scientific inquiry.

Ultimately, the effectiveness of an institution's research policies and support systems in either enhancing or dispiriting researchers hinges on how well they align with the evolving needs of both the researchers and the communities they serve. By providing the necessary resources, recognition, and opportunities, institutions can create an environment that drives high-quality, globally relevant research, while mitigating the risks of researcher disengagement and dissatisfaction.

Conclusion

This report presents the results of the APREF development, which followed an intentional, structured, and methodical approach. APREF was specifically designed to meet the unique challenges of research assessment in the ASEAN region, providing a tool that not only promotes but also measures excellence in primary care research. The framework integrates both quantitative metrics (e.g., publications, grants) and qualitative contributions (e.g., societal impact, innovation, healthcare system improvements), with each criterion weighted according to its relevance to primary care improvement and regional health outcomes. This ensures a balanced and contextually relevant assessment model.

APREF represents a pioneering initiative aimed at standardizing and enhancing research quality across ASEAN. By recognizing the region's diverse healthcare needs and resource variations, it offers a pragmatic and adaptable framework that fosters excellence in primary care research. The framework's alignment with global standards, while incorporating local insights, creates an environment that is collaborative, inclusive, and impactful. Its strong focus on accountability, the translation of research into practice, and sustainability ensures that APREF is well-positioned to significantly improve healthcare outcomes in ASEAN.

However, its long-term success will hinge on ongoing engagement from key stakeholders namely researchers, institutions, policymakers, and communities who must work together to ensure that primary care research not only achieves academic distinction but also brings meaningful improvements to public health. APREF will need to be continually tested for relevancy, consistency, and transparency in its application across different ASEAN countries, all while accounting for the region's diversity. As such, it offers both funders and decision-makers a robust tool for measuring and fostering high-impact research that can truly transform healthcare in the region.

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Conflict of interest

None declared.